

Travancore Essential Oils.

Part V.

Essential Oil from *Ageratum conyzoides*, Linn:

(Appa Grass)

BY

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Preliminary Note.

This plant is a member of the Compositae and grows wild in all places in Travancore to such an extent that it is looked upon as a pest and its growth is checked as far as possible. It is known in Trivandrum as *Muryan Pacha* (destructive green or grass), a name which is very significant. The vernacular name for the weed varies from place to place and the author got to know of it first as *Appa* grass. It can be easily distinguished by its characteristic white flowers which possess a pleasant and sweet aroma.¹ The leaves and the flowers yield an essential oil which is slightly heavier than water and possesses a powerful, almost nauseating, odour which is very persistent and, on very great dilution, resembles remotely the aroma of fresh mown hay. This explains the contrast between the strong odour of the oil and the pleasant aroma of the flowers and leaves in which the oil is very much diluted.

Appa oil appears to be simple in composition and contains about 90 per cent. of a compound, $C_{12}H_{16}O$, which is under investigation.

¹ I am obliged to Mr. Venkata Rao, the Curator of the Herbarium in the Forest Department, for the botanical note which is reproduced at the end of this paper. (page 276).

According to Murat¹ (Parry, Chem. of Ess. oils and Art. Perf., Vol. I, page 302) 500 kilos of this plant distilled with steam in Annam gave 27 grams of oil.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Five hundred pounds of the freshly cut plant (moisture=87 per cent.) were distilled with steam in a large copper still provided with a false bottom so that the plant should not come in contact with the hot surface, and the oil was collected in receivers designed for light oils and heavy oils arranged in series. About 45 c.c. of a dark brown, heavy oil were collected in the first receiver. The other receivers contained about 5 c.c. of a lighter oil; but owing to the comparatively large size of the vessels this oil had to be extracted with ether, and as the quantity obtained was too small for experiments nothing further was attempted. The colour of the heavy oil is due to a pigment and can be got rid of by distillation. The constants are given below :—

TABLE I.

	Moudgill.	Murat.
Yield (fresh grass) ...	0·02 per cent.	0·0084 per cent. (P)
" (dry grass) ...	0·16 per cent.	
" ...	invisible	-1°·20
n_D^{28} ...	1·5230	
Acid value ...	0	0·9
Ester value ...	17·4	12·1
Acetyl value ...	45·6 ^a	
d_4^{28} ...	1·008	

¹ Parry does not give a reference to the original paper by Murat.

^a The end-point of the titration was not sharp owing to the presence of the pigment referred to above which seems to undergo a colour change on boiling with alcoholic caustic potash.

A small quantity of the oil (18 c.c.) was distilled under reduced pressure and two fractions, possessing the following constants, were obtained.

TABLE II.

No.	B. pt.	†Yield.	$[\alpha]_{D}^{28^{\circ}}$	$n_{D}^{28^{\circ}}$	$d_{4}^{28^{\circ}}$
1	130°–135°/19 mm. ...	77%	$\pm 0^{\circ}$	1.5293	1.019
2	Above 135° ...	12%	...	1.5283	...
3	Residue (by difference)	...	...	...	...

A portion of the first fraction was distilled from a small bulb without decomposition.

B. pt. 254°–256°/756 mm. $n_{D}^{28^{\circ}}$ 1.5298.

It would appear, therefore, that the major portion of Appa oil consists of a liquid having the following characters :—

B. pt.	at 19 mm.	...	130°–135°
„	at 756 mm.	...	254°–256°
$d_{4}^{28^{\circ}}$	...	...	1.019
$[\alpha]_{D}^{28^{\circ}}$	...	...	$\pm 0^{\circ}$
$n_{D}^{28^{\circ}}$	...	...	1.5298

Found: C = 73.87; H = 8.72 per cent. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2$ requires
C = 74.43; H = 8.27 per cent.

† As the quantity of the oil used for fractionation was very small, the yields given above are not a very accurate measure of the proportions of the constituents. The second fraction consists very largely of the compound in fraction 1.

From its properties and constants the compound appears to be an oxide of the formula $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$, but further work is in progress and this formula is advanced only tentatively. It has not been possible to obtain the oil in quantity owing to the low yield and the difficulty of collection of the plant, but as the oil is rich in oxygenated compounds and contains only a small proportion of hydrocarbons, a more detailed investigation with larger quantities of the oil will be undertaken in August, 1925, when the plant will be in season.

The author wishes to thank Mr. I. C. Chako, Director of Industries, for defraying the cost of distillation and collection and for other help.

BOTANICAL NOTES.

Ageratum conyzoides, Linn., Annual, one to two feet high, hispidly hairy leaves, petioled, ovate, crenate, head small in dense terminal corymbs, bracts striate acute, ray flowers many, pale blue or white, achenes black, pappus scales 5 awned often serrate below.

Synonym: *Ageratum cordifolium*, Roxb., distribution throughout India, ascending the Himalayas to 5000 feet. All hot countries.

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